

MACHINE LEARNING TOPIC DETECTION OF SOCIAL MEDIA ATTITUDES ABOUT MINERAL DEVELOPMENT IN EUROPE

by

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Introduction

The green transition requires a huge amount of mineral resources to build the infrastructure and technology that produces, stores, and transmits low-carbon energy (U.S. Department of Energy, 2010). These minerals include ‘critical minerals’, which are definitionally at a high risk of supply chain disruption. The world-wide COVID-19 pandemic highlighted many of the vulnerabilities inherent in the international supply of goods and materials, including critical minerals (Giese, 2022; Zhu et al., 2020). This has also been exacerbated in Europe by the Russian invasion of Ukraine, which has caused many challenges for European energy production and distribution. Because of these vulnerabilities, it is becoming increasingly important to produce minerals as locally as possible (Kuzemko et al., 2022). At the same time, many developed economies have diversified away from primary resource production, and the idea of local mining in many member countries of the EU has become anachronistic to people who have not lived near active mining operations for many years. This has led to tension between some European developers of critical minerals and their host communities in Europe and elsewhere (Dunlap & Riquito, 2023; Eerola, 2022; Lesser et al., 2021; Ocelík et al., 2021).

Social license is a measure of the social acceptability of a given industry, organization, or project (Thomson & Boutilier, 2011). Lack of a social license in mining projects is a major risk to expensive and necessary mineral development operations across the world (Davis & Franks, 2014). Measuring and understanding the social license of the mining industry can be slow, and because the social license is a dynamic and evolving phenomenon, measurements of the social license can often lag behind the real-time sentiment and concerns of stakeholders. That is why attention has been paid in recent years to developments in natural language processing as a means of discovering and analysing issues and narratives in real time, in order to identify and ameliorate concerns before they become problems before they become insurmountable obstacles to necessary sustainable development efforts (Boutilier & Bahr, 2020). In this presentation, we discuss the use of natural language machine-learning methodologies for understanding the social license of critical mineral development in the EU.

Methodology

The SEMACRET project consists of several working packages related to geological, geophysical, and geochemical exploration at reference sites in four EU countries: The Czech Republic, Finland, Poland, and Portugal. As a part of that exploration, it is important to understand public sentiment around mining in those reference countries. In order to dynamically assess public sentiment and issues in these areas, we are searching social media for relevant texts in the four reference languages, which serve as the dataset for natural language analysis. So far, we have used an academic license to search Twitter for words related to mining in each of the languages from 2006 to early 2023, and Table 1 shows the preliminary search terms and the number of texts they produced.

Table 1 First-pass search terms by language

Language	Native Speakers (Millions)	Target Population (Millions)	Search Terms ('mining')	Tweets
Finnish	5.8	5.5	'kaivostoimintaa'	1775
Portuguese	232	10.3	'mineração' AND 'portugal'	209
Polish	40	37.8	'górnictwo'	59611
Czech	10.7	10.5	'hornictví'	624

For the most part, the number of tweets are reasonably proportionate to the size of the target population. One immediate difficulty shown in Table 1 is that Portuguese has a much higher native speaking population than that of Portugal itself. For this reason, the generic mining term "mineração" was combined with "portugal" in the initial search, in the hopes of producing only texts about mining within the reference country. This led to a disproportionately small number of tweets in Portuguese, which will be reexamined as this work progresses.

Once the data of interest were collected, we used a computational natural language processing method called Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to identify the topics that were most frequently discussed by people speaking about mining. As a statistical methodology, LDA assesses the probability that a given text is about a given topic based on the likelihood of certain words being used in that text (Blei et al., 2003; Steyvers & Griffiths, 2007). The algorithm we used is mostly language agnostic, particularly for European writing systems that use the same latin alphabet and employ similar grammatical features, e.g. discrete written words that are set apart from each other by a space (Chew & Chew, 2019; Kamyab, 2019). This means that we were able to use the same algorithm for processing all languages, with only minor modifications to the input files.

The LDA method produces "bags of words," which signify a group of words that are most likely to appear together when discussing a given topic. This requires some interpretation, in order to understand what the topic actually represents. For example, a bag that consists of the words "production," "coal," "price," "market," "cost," "electricity," "increase," "ton," and "demand" can be reasonably be interpreted to be talking about coal production. For bags of words that are more ambiguous, the LDA model gives us other contextual clues for interpreting the topics, such as the texts that contributed the most to the determination of the topic in the model, the texts that most represent the topic, and the identity of the speakers who most mentioned the topic.

The topics generated by this methodology across all four languages are shown in Table 2, which shows that the 20 topics identified in this case can be further broken into four groups. It is not surprising that the polish language data should produce its own set of distinct topics, since there were orders of magnitude more Polish texts than texts in the other languages. Polish writers also discussed many of the other topics mentioned, but the topics in the "Polish Topics" category were unique and specific to Polish writers.

Table 2 Groups of Identified Topics

Polish Topics	Legal Topics	Social Topics	Development Topics
Polska Grupa Energetyczna	Corporate Corruption	COVID in Mines	Exploration
Polish Politics	Mining Agreements	Mine Workers	Space Mining
Polish Resource Nationalism	Mining Subsidies	Unrest	Green Transition Minerals
Coal Sourcing	Mining Law	Economic Knock-on	Natural Gas
Coal Production	Regional Mining Bans	Mining History	
Climate Ministry			

After the topics have been identified, it is possible to cross-search texts for mentions of all topics, in order to determine which topics are most frequently mentioned together. This helps us to understand the larger narratives around the topics that are being created by social media users, and how individual topics are related to each other. This allows us to produce an adjacency matrix of how often each topic is mentioned with each other topic, which in turn allows us to produce and quantitatively analyze a co-mention network graph. Figure 1 shows the topic co-mention network, in which the colors of the nodes correspond to the groups in Table 2, and their vertical position within the network corresponds to their eigenvector centrality, which is a measure of a node's importance in the overall network.

Figure 1 Topic co-mention network graph

Figure 1 shows that there is a cluster of several highly connected nodes at the top, most strongly represented by the Polish topics of internal politics and resource nationalism, which are also connected to economics and general social unrest. Coal sourcing and production are connected with politics, resource nationalism, and economics, and coal sourcing is also tied to social unrest and mining subsidies. The new (2020) climate ministry of Poland is also connected to the same issues, as well as the space mining topic. On the left side of Figure 1, there is a cluster of highly connected nodes related to legal issues around mining law, regional mining bans, and mining subsidies. These topics are all related to the Polish topics, but were also mentioned by tweets from the other regions as well

Next Steps

The next major tasks have to do with refining the search terms to 1) create a more proportional sample of texts from each target language and 2) better represent native understanding of the relevant mining concepts. In order to achieve the first task, the search terms will be expanded and more nuanced search criteria will be implemented. This task will also be helped by the second task, in which native speaking SEMACRET partner members will help to correct improper grammar and syntax in the search terms. It has been pointed out, for example that of the Polish words to describe mining, "górnictwo," doesn't have the same functional meaning as the words in the other languages. Having native speakers to help with the data collection phase will help us to produce more relevant topic models and develop a better sense of the topics that cross cultural and linguistic boundaries.

In addition to the above next steps topic analysis and other quantitative linguistic methods will be applied to each language individually, so that the country specific issues can also be better identified and understood. These improvements will help to develop a real-time social media monitor that can help to study mining related issues as they emerge and evolve.

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